

Path Dependency and Angular Anisoplanatism in Non-Kolmogorov Turbulence

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Abstract—We examine the effect of non-Kolmogorov turbulence on angular anisoplanatism. Generalized expressions for the isoplanatic angle in turbulence with non-Kolmogorov power-laws are developed in terms of the effective turbulence height, related turbulence moments, and characteristics lengths such as Striblings equivalent Fried parameter. We then compare the effective turbulence height and isoplanatic angle using the Hufnagel-Valley 5-7 (HV 5-7) and Mauna Kea (HV-MK) turbulence profiles at both the upper and lower power-law limits. In addition, using the HV-MK profile we consider the effect of a single non-Kolmogorov turbulent shear layer. We find that, for fixed path length and spatial coherence, a smaller power-law reduces the isoplanatic angle while larger power-laws increase it relative to the Kolmogorov case. In contrast, when the turbulence strength profile is fixed smaller power law exponent the isoplanatic angle increases and decreases when the power law exponent is larger than the Kolmogorov value. Similar results are shown for the case of non-Kolmogorov shear layers.

first define what we mean by Kolmogorov turbulence. The Kolmogorov model for turbulence is a statistical description for the random index of refraction variations observed in the atmosphere [7]. These variations are assumed to be isotropic and stationary in first increments. Mathematically, we also assume these fluctuations can be described using structure function with a $2/3$ power-law. Strictly speaking, any deviation from these assumptions delves into the realm of non-Kolmogorov turbulence [8], [9]. In this paper, and most other works on the topic [10], [11], the focus is on a change of power-law. Other modifications, such as finite inner and outer scales, and modifications to the dissipation range are considered to be within the scope of Kolmogorov turbulence and are not addressed here.

Most of the foundational work in atmospheric imaging and adaptive optics dates back to the early 1960s [7][3]. So, it is with some reservation that we revisit these well-tread topics. However, there is now strong evidence suggesting that distortions caused by features such as Von Karman vortex streets, temperature sheets, and atmospheric shear layers in the upper atmosphere are not well described by Kolmogorov theory [12], [13], [14]. The engagement/imaging path of every astronomical and Space Situational Awareness (SSA) telescope must traverse areas where these structures are hypothesized to exist. Therefore, it is important to revisit these topics and contemplate the effects of non-Kolmogorov turbulence on the performance of imaging systems.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In adaptive optics (AO), the isoplanatic angle defines the maximum angle between a point reference, either an artificial or natural guide star, and the imaging target over which atmospheric turbulence can be adequately compensated [1], [2]. Along with the Fried parameter, the isoplanatic angle is one of the most important in AO system engineering. For both parameters, stronger turbulence along the imaging path degrades viewing conditions, decreasing the coherence radius (Fried parameter) [3] and the field of view corrected by the AO system in the case of the isoplanatic angle [4], [5]. However, the isoplanatic angle is sensitive to the distribution of turbulence along the imaging path whereas the Fried parameter depends only on the average value. Specifically, turbulence near to the object being observed has a greater effect than the turbulence near to the telescope with a $5/3$ path weighting in Kolmogorov turbulence [6]. The $5/3$ weighting clearly originates with from the $2/3$ power-law description of Kolmogorov turbulence. This dependence motivates our examination into how non-Kolmogorov with varied power-laws may affect this path weighting and associated parameters.

To properly define non-Kolmogorov turbulence we must

Light reaching Earth from a distant star can be thought of as being equivalent to an unbounded plane wave. The flat wave front is perturbed as it interacts with the random index of refraction fluctuations caused by turbulence in the atmosphere. These perturbations distort acquired imagery reducing its value. Adaptive optics systems compensate for these fluctuations by coupling a Wave Front Sensor (WFS) and a deformable mirror (DM) to a control system. The WFS measures the wave-front distortion by observing a bright, nearby, natural or artificial guide star. The measured wave-front distortions are provided to the control system which commands the DM such that surface is conjugate to the wave-front distortion. In a perfectly corrected AO system the image of the reference star will appear as a diffraction-limited Airy disc. The quality of other objects within the systems field of view will depend on the relative wavefront error between the reference and target object. This error arises due to the line-of-sight path differences between the reference and the target through the turbulence volume. The resulting wavefront error is referred to as angular anisoplanatism and referred to as such to distinguish it from other forms of anisoplanatism such as focus or displacement [1]. Angular anisoplanatism increases as a function of angular separation and is one of the major factors contributing to the degradation of AO system performance. The point at which the mean-squared anisoplanatic error equals 1 rad^2 is commonly referred to as

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the isoplanatic angle. Typical values of the isoplanatic angle are on the order of a few arcseconds for mountaintop sites under good viewing conditions.

Anisoplanatism is also a dominant source of distortion in horizontal imaging systems used in Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance (ISR) applications. In these scenarios the field of view is generally much larger and the turbulence, being near the ground, is more severe. Consequently, anisoplanatism is manifested as tip and tilt distortions that vary over the scene [15]. The spatial-variance of the image distortion poses a significant hurdle for most image reconstruction algorithms preferred here for scene enhancement in place of AO systems.

The aim of this paper is to explore the effect of non-Kolmogorov turbulence on the isoplanatic angle. Specifically, because anisoplanatism is a path dependent phenomenon we wish to understand how a change in power-law exponent changes this path dependency. We start our investigation in Section 2 by reviewing the derivation of the isoplanatic angle under the assumption of Kolmogorov turbulence. This derivation is generalized in Section 3 and new expressions for the isoplanatic angle in non-Kolmogorov turbulence are presented. In this section we also comment on the effect of changing power-law on isoplanatic angle in the special case where spatial coherence and path length are fixed. Next, we review two popular turbulence path-height models for the refractive index structure parameter based on the Hufnagel-Stanley model. In Section 3 we use these models to examine the effects of both a shift in power-law along the entire path and the effect of introducing a strong, non-Kolmogorov shear layer above a nadir-pointed telescope. Conclusions and suggestions for future work are provided in Section 4.

2. BACKGROUND

The isoplanatic angle is defined here and elsewhere as [2]

$$\theta_0 = \left[2.91k^2 \int_0^L C_n^2(z) z^{5/3} dz \right]^{-3/5} \quad (1)$$

Our goal in this paper is to determine a generalized form for this expression and examine how a change in power-law exponent is manifested in angular anisoplanatism. It is worthwhile to begin by deconstructing this expression and explaining consequences with respect to path weighting, etc. In Eq.1, k is the optical wavenumber, $C_n^2(z)$ is the refractive index structure parameter, which we note is a function of the path defined by variable z between $z = 0$ and $z = L$. Following astronomical convention $z = 0$ at the telescope or imaging system and $z = L$ at either the source or the edge of the atmosphere. If the path is reversed such that the $z = 0$ at the source the expression becomes

$$\theta_0 = \left[2.91k^2 L^{5/3} \int_0^L C_n^2(z) \left(1 - \frac{z}{L}\right)^{5/3} dz \right]^{-3/5} \quad (2)$$

It is clear from Eq.1 and Eq.2 that isoplanatic angle has a $5/3$ path weighting so that turbulence far from the telescope, and near to the source, contributes more significantly to the isoplanatic angle. Contrast this expression with the one for

the Fried parameter for a plane wave, p_w , source

$$r_{0,pw} = \left[0.423k^2 \int_0^L C_n^2(z) dz \right]^{-3/5} \quad (3)$$

Both Eq.1 and Eq.3 depend on the integrated turbulence strength along the imaging path. However, the integral in Eq.3 does not have a path dependency. Consequently, in the plane wave case, measuring r_0 provides no information about the distribution of turbulence along 0 to L . In contrast, consider the expression for spherical wave (sw), r_0 using the astronomical, telescope-centric, convention from Eq.1

$$r_{0,sw} = \left[0.423k^2 \int_0^L C_n^2(z) \left(1 - \frac{z}{L}\right)^{5/3} dz \right]^{-3/5} \quad (4)$$

and the source-centric convention of Eq.2 as

$$r_{0,sw} = \left[0.423k^2 \int_0^L C_n^2(z) \left(\frac{z}{L}\right)^{5/3} dz \right]^{-3/5} \quad (5)$$

Comparing Eq.4 and Eq.5 to Eq.1 and Eq.2 we note that that path weighting is reversed. That is to say, turbulence near to the telescope more strongly affects the spatial coherence of a spherical wave source observed by an imaging system. This duality has been successfully used [6], [16] to infer information about the distribution of turbulence along the imaging path.

Due to the common presence of these path weighting parameters in quantities relevant to optical propagation through atmospheric turbulence it is convenient to define these weightings in terms of turbulence moments such that

$$\mu_m = \int_0^\infty C_n^2(z) z^m dz \quad (6)$$

It is clear from Eq.6 that Eq.3 and Eq.1 can be written in terms of the $m = 0$ and $m = 5/3$ moments respectively. Relative to this work, the turbulence moments are also important in defining the mean turbulence height [2]

$$\bar{h} = \left(\frac{\mu_{5/3}}{\mu_0} \right)^{3/5} \quad (7)$$

and describes the effective height at which the turbulence appears to exist with respect to an observer.

As mentioned in the introduction, the isoplanatic angle defines the separation at which the difference in the wavefront is equal to 1 rad^2 . The expression in Eq.1 is found via the Wave Structure Function (WSF), for an unbounded plane wave in weak turbulence the WSF is

$$D(\rho) = 2.914k^2 \rho^{5/3} \int_0^L C_n^2(z) dz \quad (8)$$

The WSF defines the mean squared error at an in-plane separation ρ . Setting Eq.8 to $D(\rho) = 1$ and $\rho = \theta L$ and solving for θ results in the expression in Eq.1. Similarly, Eq.3 results from setting $D(r_0) = 6.88$.

3. RESULTS

The isoplanatic angle in Non-Kolmogorov turbulence

From the discussion in the previous section it should be obvious that all that is required to define the isoplanatic angle in non-Kolmogorov turbulence is an expression for the WSF for arbitrary power law exponents. The values of which are limited here for both physical and practical reasons to $3 < \alpha < 4$. From [9] and elsewhere [8], [7], this expression is given as

$$D(\rho) = 8\pi^2 k^2 A(\alpha) \left(2^{-\alpha} \alpha \frac{\Gamma\left[-\frac{\alpha}{2}\right]}{\Gamma\left[\frac{\alpha}{2}\right]} \right) \rho^{\alpha-2} \int_0^L dz \tilde{C}_n^2(z) \quad (9)$$

In Eq.9, $A(\alpha) = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \Gamma(\alpha - 1) \cos\left(\frac{\alpha\pi}{2}\right)$ is a term that maintains consistency between structure function and spectral representation of turbulence fluctuations and the refractive index structure function. Also, C_n^2 which has units of $\text{m}^{-2/3}$ in Kolmogorov turbulence has been generalized to an equivalent parameter \tilde{C}_n^2 with units $\text{m}^{3-\alpha}$. Replacing ρ with θL results in

$$D(\theta) = 8\pi^2 k^2 A(\alpha) \left(2^{-\alpha} \alpha \frac{\Gamma\left[-\frac{\alpha}{2}\right]}{\Gamma\left[\frac{\alpha}{2}\right]} \right) \theta^{\alpha-2} \times \int_0^L \tilde{C}_n^2(z) z^{\alpha-2} dz \quad (10)$$

Finally, setting $D(\tilde{\theta}_0) = 1$ and solving for $\tilde{\theta}_0$ provides the following expression for the isoplanatic angle in an arbitrary power-law media

$$\tilde{\theta}_0 = \left[8\pi^2 k^2 A(\alpha) \left(2^{-\alpha} \alpha \frac{\Gamma\left[-\frac{\alpha}{2}\right]}{\Gamma\left[\frac{\alpha}{2}\right]} \right) \int_0^L \tilde{C}_n^2(z) z^{\alpha-2} dz \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha-2}} \quad (11)$$

At this point it is difficult to draw conclusions about the effect of a deviation in power-law away from the Kolmogorov norm. Noting our bounds $3 < \alpha < 4$, we observe that at $\alpha = 3$ the isoplanatic angle is inversely proportional to the argument inside the brackets in Eq.11. To be clear, the expression in Eq.11 is not valid at $\alpha = 3$ because the consistency factor, $A(\alpha)$ evaluates to zero. Similarly, the expression inside the parentheses in Eq.11 evaluates to complex infinity when $\alpha = 4$ where the isoplanatic varies as the square root of the argument in the brackets. Though, in both cases, these notions are consistent with the corresponding structure function definition where the square phase error varies linearly at $\alpha = 3$ and with ρ^2 at $\alpha = 4$.

Additional insight can be gained by recasting the isoplanatic angle in terms of the turbulence moments. As noted earlier, there is a definite relationship between the quantities Eq.1, 3 and 6. Following Hardy [2]

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\theta_0}{r_{0,pw}} &= \left[\frac{6.88 \int_0^L C_n^2(z) z^{5/3} dz}{\int_0^L C_n^2(z) dz} \right]^{-3/5} \\ &= \left[6.88 \frac{\mu_{5/3}}{\mu_0} \right]^{-3/5} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Bringing in Eq.7 we can write the isoplanatic angle as a function of the Fried's coherence length and the mean turbulence height.

$$\theta_0 = (6.88)^{-3/5} \frac{r_0}{\tilde{h}} \quad (13)$$

Figure 1. Relative isoplanatic angle at fixed \tilde{h} and \tilde{r}_0 for arbitrary power-law normalized to the Kolmogorov value of 0.314.

The constant in Eq.13 evaluates to $(6.88)^{-3/5} = 0.314$ and in the constant turbulence case reduces to the common handbook expression $\theta_0 = 0.314 r_0 / L$.

The constant 6.88 is taken from Fried's analysis of the resolution available in a turbulence-limited, infinite-aperture imaging system and is valid in Kolmogorov turbulence. In [8] Stribling generalized this parameter as

$$c_1(\alpha) = 2 \left(\frac{8}{\alpha - 2} \Gamma \left[\frac{2}{\alpha - 2} \right] \right)^{\frac{\alpha-2}{2}} \quad (14)$$

Substituting $c_1(\alpha)$ for the constant 6.88 in Eq.13 provides

$$\tilde{\theta}_0 = c_1(\alpha)^{-\frac{1}{\alpha-2}} \left(\frac{\tilde{r}_0}{\tilde{h}} \right) \quad (15)$$

Where the mean turbulence height, \tilde{h} , has been modified to account for arbitrary power laws.

$$\tilde{h} = \left(\frac{\mu_{\alpha-2}}{\mu_0} \right)^{-\frac{1}{\alpha-2}} \quad (16)$$

Using Eq.15 we can now examine the effect of a change in power law on the isoplanatic angle by fixing the coherence length and the mean turbulence height. In this case, the effect of a change in power law can be understood by examining the preceding constant, $c_1(\alpha)^{-1/(\alpha-2)}$. We have plotted this constant normalized to the Kolmogorov value of 0.314 in Fig.1.

From the figure we can conclude that the isoplanatic angle is roughly proportional to the power-law for a fixed observation path and coherence radius. Under these assumptions an increase in power-law will increase the isoplanatic angle and patch size. Similarly, a decrease in power-law will result in a smaller isoplanatic region under the assumptions of fixed turbulence height and spatial coherence.

Turbulence Profiles based on the Hufnagel-Valley model

In this section, we explore the effect of a change in power-law on the mean turbulence height and isoplanatic angle when a realistic turbulence strength path-height model is used. We examine two parameterized path height models based on the Hufnagel-Valley model [2]

$$C_n^2(h) = A \exp\left(-\frac{h}{H_A}\right) + B \exp\left(-\frac{h}{H_B}\right) + Ch^{10} \exp\left(-\frac{h}{H_C}\right) + D \exp\left(-\frac{(h-H_D)^2}{2d^2}\right) \quad (17)$$

The first model we examine is the common HV 5-7 profile [17] which has parameters $A = 1.7 \times 10^{-14}$, $H_A = 100$ m, $B = 2.7 \times 10^{-16}$, $H_B = 1500$ m, $C = 3.59 \times 10^{-53}$, $H_C = 1000$ m. Constants related to the last term in Eq.17 are not defined in the HV 5-7 model and are therefore set to zero. The HV 5-7 profile is a reasonable general profile useful in describing turbulence strength and includes accommodation for ground-layer turbulence, which can be severe.

The HV-MK [18], [2] model has parameters $B = 1 \times 10^{-16}$, $H_B = 3000$ m, $C = 1.63 \times 10^{-53}$, $H_C = 1000$ m and is generally used for describing the seeing from mountaintop sites, such as Haleakala and Mauna Kea in Hawaii. This model does not include the ground-layer turbulence term, found in Eq.17, but does include a strong turbulence shear layer from the last term. The parameters for the shear layer are [2] $D = 10^{-16}$, $H_D = 6500$ m, and $d = 300$ m. The height and width of the shear layer can be controlled in this model by varying H_D and d respectively. Both profiles are plotted together in Fig.2.

The mean turbulence height for the HV 5-7 is $\bar{h} = 2259$ m and 8096 m for the HV-MK model when the power-law is Kolmogorov. Changing the power law to $\alpha = 3.1$ has the effect of lowering the mean turbulence height to $\tilde{h} = 1161$ m in the HV 5-7 case and 7581 m for the HV-MK case. In both cases, lowering the effective turbulence height should reduce anisoplanatism. Equivalently, we would expect to see a corresponding increase in the isoplanatic angle. Increasing the power-law to $\alpha = 3.9$ results in a corresponding increase in the mean turbulence height to $\bar{h} = 2724$ m and 8294 m for the HV 5-7 and HV-MK profiles, respectively. In this case, we expect the increase in mean turbulence height should result decrease isoplanatic angle.

Using Eq.1 the isoplanatic angle evaluates as 6.89μ radians in the HV 5-7 case. Following our prediction, when the power-law is decreased to $\alpha = 3.1$ the isoplanatic angle increases to 12.16μ rad, a 76% increase. Similarly, in the HV-MK case the isoplanatic angle increases roughly doubles to 19.97μ rad. Increasing the power-law to $\alpha = 3.9$ reduces the isoplanatic angle to 4.95μ rad for the HV 5-7 profile and 6.43μ rad for the HV-MK profile.

Of course, purely non-Kolmogorov turbulence is unlikely and our interest in exploring these effects is ultimately motivated by our desire to understand general effects of non-Kolmogorov layers in the atmosphere. In this manner, the HV-MK profile provides a method whereby the effect of a non-Kolmogorov shear layer can be explored directly.

Consider again Eq.10, this expression describes the mean-squared wavefront error as a function of angle, θ . As in [2] we refer to this error as the anisoplanatic error, $\langle \sigma_\theta^2 \rangle$. After substitution of Eq.17 in to Eq.10 we see that the

integration over each term in the turbulence profile can be taken independently. Taking the last term to represent the shear layer with a generalized exponent and the remaining terms as background turbulence with Kolmogorov statistics we can write,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \sigma_\theta^2 \rangle = & 2.914k^2\theta^{5/3} \int_0^L \left(A \exp\left(-\frac{z}{H_A}\right) \right. \\ & + B \exp\left(-\frac{z}{H_B}\right) + Ch^{10} \exp\left(-\frac{z}{H_C}\right) \left. \right) z^{5/3} dz \\ & + 8\pi^2 k^2 A(\alpha) \left(2^{-\alpha} \alpha \frac{\Gamma\left[-\frac{\alpha}{2}\right]}{\Gamma\left[\frac{\alpha}{2}\right]} \right) \theta^{\alpha-2} \\ & \int_0^L D \exp\left(-\frac{(z-H_D)^2}{2d^2}\right) z^{\alpha-2} dz \quad (18) \end{aligned}$$

The anisoplanatic error as described by Eq.18 is plotted in Fig.3 for three different values of shear-layer power law exponent, α_s at a wavelength of $\lambda = 500$ nm and using the parameters for the HV-MK profile described above. The background turbulence case, with no shear layer, is also included in the figure. Considering only background turbulence, the isoplanatic angle is 11.59μ rad. Adding the Kolmogorov, $\alpha_s = 11/3$ shear layer reduces the isoplanatic angle to 10.15μ rad. A shear layer at $\alpha = 3.1$ decreases the anisoplanatic error relative to the Kolmogorov shear layer case to 10.86μ rad. While a $\alpha_s = 3.9$ shear layer reduces the isoplanatic angle to 9.28μ rad.

4. CONCLUSION

We have investigated the effects of non-Kolmogorov turbulence on angular anisoplanatism, the associated path-weighting factor and isoplanatic angle. It is well known that, in the Kolmogorov case, the isoplanatic angle is dependent on the mean turbulence height, defined as the ratio of the $5/3$, $\mu_{5/3}$, and the zero-th, μ_0 , order turbulence moments. The $5/3$ term here is associated with the two-dimensional Kolmogorov power-law and so it is no surprise that a change to the power-law affects the observed isoplanatic angle. Consequently, in non-Kolmogorov turbulence, defined by a change in power-law between $3 < \alpha < 4$, the isoplanatic angle varies as the ratio of the $\mu_{\alpha-2}$, turbulence moment to μ_0 ; the mean turbulence height in non-Kolmogorov turbulence. We note that if $\alpha = 11/3$ this expression matches exactly the Kolmogorov case. From this relationship, and using Striblings coherence parameter, we were able to define the isoplanatic angle for an imaging path with a fixed spatial coherence and mean turbulence height. In this case, the isoplanatic angle increases with the power-law so that if the power-law is smaller than the Kolmogorov value so is the isoplanatic angle and vice versa. In a more general sense, we can conclude that the isoplanatic angle increases with power-law when spatial coherence is fixed and when the turbulence does not vary over the imaging path.

Starting with the generalized WSF we also developed an expression for the anisoplanatic error and isoplanatic angle in non-Kolmogorov turbulence. We then demonstrated the effect of a change in power law on the isoplanatic angle when the distribution of turbulence strength along the imaging path is held constant. Two turbulence path-height models were explored, the HV 5-7 and the HV-MK model. In both cases, we found that the isoplanatic angle decreases with increasing power-law; exactly the opposite result as the constant coherence case. Here we conclude that for a given turbulence distribution the anisoplanatic error increases with power-law and therefore the isoplanatic angle decreases. This conclusion

Figure 2. Turbulence height profiles based on the Hufnagel-Valley model. The HV 5-7 model includes a ground layer term, where as the model has no ground layer term and includes a strong shear layer (dashed) at 6500 m.

Figure 3. Anisoplanatic error, $\langle \sigma_\theta^2 \rangle$ as a function of angular separation θ for a shear layer with varied power-law (dashed) exponent compared to the case with no shear layer (bold)

also applies to the case where the background turbulence is Kolmogorov and non-Kolmogorov turbulence exists as a strong shear layer along the imaging path.

The apparent contradiction in our findings highlights one of the difficulties in comparing Kolmogorov to non-Kolmogorov turbulence. Specifically, because of the change in power-law, the units of \tilde{C}_n^2 vary as $\text{m}^{3-\alpha}$. To that point, consider three turbulence volumes described by the range of power laws considered here. Take the first as having a power law near $\alpha \approx 3$, the second as being Kolmogorov $\alpha = 11/3$ and the last near $\alpha \approx 4$. The corresponding refractive index structure functions will all evaluate to the same value at a separation of $\rho = 1$ m. However, the values at any other location are very different. For example, at a separation of $\rho = 2$ m the low, Kolmogorov and high cases evaluate to 1, 1.5, and 2 times \tilde{C}_n^2 respectively.

It has been pointed out elsewhere [19] that such comparisons can lead to incorrect conclusions with respect to the effect of a change in power law on field statistics. No doubt that is also true here. However, we assert that both conclusions are useful when properly applied. We first concluded that isoplanatic angle increases generally for fixed spatial coherence. This conclusion applies in general and requires no caveats. However, we also concluded that the isoplanatic angle decreases with power-law exponent for a fixed turbulence-height profile. This conclusion is only valid when both the structure parameter and power-law are measured, as in [12] for example. Similarly, we conclude our methodology correctly predicts the affect of a non-Kolmogorov shear layer when the value of \tilde{C}_n^2 is known.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was performed while the author held a National Research Council Research Associateship Award at the Air Force Research Lab. The views expressed in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the Department of Defense or its components. Rao Gudimetla was partially supported during the progress of this work by the Air Force Office of Scientific Research.

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